
CSCCE Glossary: Project Management

Introduction

Many community managers are also expected to manage projects, often without any formal project management training. That's why we've developed a seven-session [Project Management for Scientists Bootcamp \(PMB\)](#) to support the exploration of key project management concepts, with a strong emphasis on the interpersonal skills needed for successful collaborative work. The training draws upon a core text, [The Harvard Business Review Project Management Handbook](#) by Antonio Nieto-Rodriguez, with materials contextualized for STEM scenarios and applied to custom STEM case studies by CSCCE staff.

This glossary curates many of the terms used both in the reference text book and throughout the training, with a view to supporting the learning experience of course participants. Where relevant, we have included a reference to the page (or pages) where a term appears in the book.

The terms defined in this document form part of our wider Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) glossary, [a growing resource on our website](#), which also includes language from our other frameworks and courses. It is a work in progress, and we're adding new sections all the time. As we add new sections, we're also creating PDF records like this one, which you can cite if you find our definitions of terms helpful.

We welcome feedback on the terms included as well as suggestions of additions, and encourage you to [join the conversations](#) in our community of practice.

About CSCCE

The Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) champions the importance of human infrastructure for effective collaboration in STEM. We provide training and support for the people who make scientific collaborations succeed at scale and we also research the impact of these emerging roles.

Find out more about us on our website: cscce.org

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This sub-section of the glossary was written by CSCCE staff members. CSCCE uses the CRediT contributor roles taxonomy to show how the authors listed contributed to the creation of this guide:

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AGILE

An iterative project management approach that is used when the final requirements cannot be accurately defined ahead of time and are worked out collaboratively. Examples include **Scrum** and **Kanban**.

ALIGNMENT

How emotionally connected a project team and stakeholders feel to the project, i.e., how passionate they feel about the purpose of the project. One of the three constraints in the **Engagement triple constraint**. (Chapter 6, p. 122)

BENEFIT

A positive outcome from a project that creates value for the project's stakeholders. Some benefits may be generated before the entire project has been completed, e.g., because one deliverable is ready before others. One of the **Foundation** domain building blocks in the **Project Canvas**. (Chapter 5, p. 91)

BENEFITS CARD

A checklist tool for identifying the various benefits a project is intended to deliver to different **stakeholders**. From this, the top three benefits of the project may be agreed upon. (Chapter 5, p. 91)

BENEFITS PLAN

A plan that describes the benefits the project is intended to deliver (as determined by the **benefits card**) and when they will be delivered. Note that some benefits may be realized after completion of the project. (Chapter 5, p. 92)

BENEFITS TRIPLE CONSTRAINT

A framework showing how three constraints — the potential **value** a project might deliver, the **risks** that may be involved in delivering the project, and the long-term **sustainability** of the benefits — relate to each other and affect the overall **benefits** that a project could deliver. (Chapter 5, p. 89)

BUDGET

The total resources needed for a project, including team time, management time, and other costs like consultants, materials, and equipment. (Chapter 5, p. 82)

CHANGE

One of the building blocks of the **Creation** domain of the **Project Canvas**. It is concerned with how risk will be managed and stakeholders will be engaged in the change management process. (Chapter 4, p. 69)

COMPLEXITY

One of two factors (along with **uncertainty**) that determine the type of project and its likelihood of success. Complexity is determined by the project's size, scope, stakeholder count, and stakeholder **alignment**. (Chapter 2, p. 33)

CREATION DOMAIN

One of the three **Project Canvas** domains, containing three building blocks: **Deliverables**, **Plan**, and **Change**. (Chapter 4, p. 69, and Chapter 7, pp. 129-163)

DELIVERABLE

A significant, final output produced from the project and delivered to stakeholders that helps achieve the project's **purpose** and **benefits**. All deliverables are outputs (or multiple outputs), but not all outputs may be deliverables. One of the **Creation** domain building blocks in the **Project Canvas**. (Chapter 4, p. 69, and Chapter 7, pp. 129 -131)

DEDICATION

The amount of time team members and stakeholders commit to the project. One of the three constraints in the **Engagement triple constraint** (Chapter 6, pp. 113-115)

EFFICIENCY PROJECT

Projects that help an organization, group, or team operate more efficiently. The project goals are relatively clear, often driven by external or internal requirements. These projects typically have low to medium complexity with well-defined scope, and may involve compliance work or iterative improvements like updates. (Chapter 2, p. 34)

EMERGENT COSTS

A budgeting approach where the leadership team agrees on a budget for a set period (e.g., six months) and then reassesses for the next phase. This cycle is repeated as needed throughout the project.

ENGAGEMENT TRIPLE CONSTRAINT

A framework showing how three constraints — a project team's **alignment**, **dedication**, and **recognition** — interact and influence overall team engagement. (Chapter 6, p. 122)

FOUNDATION DOMAIN

One of three Project Canvas domains that establishes the project's basis — its purpose, costs, and benefits. Contains three building blocks: **Purpose**, **Investment**, and **Benefits**. (Chapter 4, p. 69, and Chapter 5, pp. 73-94)

FUNCTIONAL UNIT

A team made up of members with similar expertise or backgrounds. It can exist within a formal organizational structure or be created temporarily for a specific project.

INVESTMENT

All project costs, including team time and other required resources to complete the project. Also called the project budget. One of the **Foundation** domain building blocks in the **Project Canvas**. (Chapter 5, p. 82)

KANBAN

An agile project management approach that visualizes the project's workflows on a shared project board. Work is pulled from a backlog of tasks into the active lane of the project board, limiting work-in-progress to match capacity, and avoiding bottlenecks. Once work is completed it is moved to the completed lane. It supports the team in being able to see where every task on the project currently stands. (Chapter 3, p. 51)

MILESTONE

A checkpoint in a project that signifies the completion of a significant deliverable(s) or phase of the project along the path to project completion. Can be a good opportunity to celebrate progress so far and review any lessons learned for the next phase.

OPERATIONS

A group, team, or organization's routine daily activities that follow consistent patterns each year with minor improvements. Operations are repetitive, often automated, and handled by dedicated staff.

OUTCOME

The impact created by a project's **output** such as a change in behavior, or measurable improvement in efficiency.

OUTPUT

A specific asset produced by a project, such as a new feature, piece of documentation, or lesson plan. Outputs may be intermediate steps on the way to a larger project **deliverable**.

PEOPLE DOMAIN

One of three **Project Canvas** domains describing the personnel working on or affected by a project. Contains three building blocks: **Sponsorship**, **Stakeholders**, and **Resources**. (Chapter 4, p. 69, and Chapter 6, 97-127)

PLAN

One of the building blocks of the **Creation** domain of the **Project Canvas** which describes how and when work on the project will occur. (Chapter 4, p. 69, and Chapter 7, pp.142-151)

PROGRAM

A collection of related projects that together deliver a capability — the structures, processes, skills, or knowledge — that enable new behaviors. Programs are higher-level project structures. (Chapter 3, p. 48)

PROGRAM MANAGEMENT

Managing several related projects to deliver a strategic capability like capacity building. Focuses on coordinating resources, managing connections between projects, and overseeing overall costs and risks. Used for high-complexity projects with low to medium uncertainty. (Chapter 3, p. 48)

PROJECT

An undertaking that requires financial and human resources, brings together people with diverse expertise who haven't worked together before, and includes unique elements — something never done before. Projects are vehicles for change. (Chapter 2, p. 29)

PROJECT CANVAS

A framework for examining and describing a project's key elements. Includes three domains (**Foundation**, **People**, and **Creation**) with three building blocks each. (Chapter 3, pp. 57-58)

PROJECT GOVERNANCE

How decisions are made about the project, the roles and responsibilities on a project, how stakeholders will be engaged in giving input and feedback, and how the project will be managed. May look like codified values, processes, and structures etc. (Chapter 6, p. 102)

PROJECT LEADERSHIP

A term describing the combined role of both **project sponsors** and **project managers**. The *HBR Project Management Handbook* describes how effective project leaders have seven key characteristics: (1) project management skills; (2) product development and domain expertise; (3) strategy and

business acumen; (4) leadership and change management; (5) agility and adaptability; (6) ethics and values; and (7) a positive attitude. CSCCE adapted these qualities and competencies for STEM as follows: (2) domain expertise or fluency; (3) strategy and ecosystem awareness. (Chapter 2, pp. 31-32)

PROJECT MANAGER

The person in charge of coordinating the planning and delivery of a project. (Chapter 2, p. 31)

PROJECT PORTFOLIO

All of the projects that a group or organization is pursuing. Centralized portfolio management (e.g., by a PI of a research group), involves selecting, prioritizing, and managing projects by considering them as investments of resources that are intended to drive change and produce defined benefits. Effective portfolio management aligns the projects with the group's overarching strategic goals. It also optimizes the use of limited resources, and makes connections between projects in the portfolio, including by balancing the number of projects of different types (**efficiency**, **sustaining**, and **transformative**) to match the available resources. (Chapter 2, p. 31)

PROJECT PURPOSE

The project's fundamental reason for existing, including outlining the problem the project will address or the change that will be brought about by completing the project. An effective purpose inspires the intrinsic motivations of the project team. One of the **Foundation** domain building blocks in the **Project Canvas**. (Chapter 5, p. 75)

PROJECT SPONSOR

This person is the link between the organization funding the project and the team delivering it. Often this is the PI or co-PI of a grant, and they may also be called the executive sponsor. They hold a critical role in the project's success, especially as complexity increases, because they influence the project's scope, direction, and budget. Sponsorship is one of the building blocks of the **People** domain of the **Project Canvas**. (Chapter 6, pp. 98-99)

RACI MATRIX

A tool used to define roles related to decision-making on a project. The matrix distinguishes roles by who is **R**esponsible for individual tasks that contribute to project deliverables, who is **A**ccountable for the overall deliverable, who ought to be **C**onsulted before decisions are made, and who ought to be kept **I**nformed of decisions (but do not need to be involved in the day-to-day work).

RECOGNITION

When team members feel they're contributing to the project and receiving appropriate acknowledgment for their role. One of the three constraints in the **Engagement triple constraint** (Chapter 6, pp. 113, 122).

RESOURCES

Everyone actively working on the project — including the project manager who will be supporting the optimal functioning of the team. Resources is one of the building blocks of the **People** domain of the **Project Canvas**. (Chapter 6, pp. 98, 108)

SCOPE CREEP

When the original scope of the project is changed, often incrementally and without deliberate changes to the project plan or project investment, such that the end deliverables of the project may no longer adequately address the project's purpose or deliver all of the benefits identified at the beginning of the project. Careful stakeholder management may be needed to avoid scope creep. (Chapter 7, p. 137)

SCOPE STATEMENT

A description of the project's outputs and deliverables, as well as what's excluded from the project at this stage. It captures any key assumptions about the project and can be useful in managing the expectations of stakeholders, including to avoid **scope creep**. (Chapter 7, p. 132)

SCRUM

An iterative project management approach that organizes work into sprints — focused periods where specific milestones or tasks are completed before moving to the next sprint. Each sprint follows consistent roles, responsibilities, and meetings. (Chapter 7, p. 136)

STAKEHOLDERS

People or organizations outside of your community who have a vested interest in the community's success, which may include benefiting from the activities of the community. Internal stakeholders are often team members directly impacted by the outcomes, while external stakeholders are not part of the organization but have an interest in the project (e.g., funders or related communities). Stakeholders is one of the building blocks of the **People** domain of the **Project Canvas**. (Chapter 6, pp. 98, 119)

Note: Use of the word "stakeholder" is currently a topic of debate, which you can [read more about in this article](#).

STEERING COMMITTEE

A group of expert **stakeholders** providing guidance throughout a project. May also help determine or manage a **project portfolio**, depending on context. (Chapter 6, p. 102)

SUSTAINING PROJECT

Projects that grow and expand the group's area of focus such as developing new products or services e.g., a new training course or a new assay. These projects start with medium to high **uncertainty** — the path to the desired outcome isn't necessarily clear. They typically have medium **complexity** and require building shared expectations, defining success upfront, and avoiding **scope creep**. (Chapter 2, p. 34)

TRADITIONAL PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Project management methods that define the full scope and create a complete plan before starting work. Also called waterfall or predictive approaches. Best suited for projects with medium complexity and uncertainty.

TRANSFORMATIVE PROJECT

This type of project results in radical innovations that dramatically change what an organization, group, or team can do in the future, e.g., by developing a brand-new technology. These are the riskiest, most challenging, and innovative projects and have high **uncertainty** and **complexity**, requiring significant collaboration and creativity. (Chapter 2, p. 34)

TRIPLE CONSTRAINT

The relationship between a project's scope, cost, and time, and how these factors affect output quality. Also called the iron triangle. The *HBR Project Management Handbook* proposes two new variants of the triple constraint: the **benefits triple constraint** and the **engagement triple constraint**. (Chapter 3, p. 58)

UNCERTAINTY

One of two factors (along with **complexity**) determining project type and success likelihood. Determined by the project's novelty, team experience, and clarity around project features and budget. (Chapter 2, p. 35)

WORK BREAKDOWN STRUCTURE (WBS)

A systematic way of defining all project work by organizing project components into a product-oriented hierarchy or "family tree." (Definition adapted from the Project Management Institute, as cited in the *HBR Project Management Handbook*, Chapter 7, p. 133)

Citing and reusing this guide

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